

Content warnings: mentions of trauma, aversive, violent and abusive therapies, suicide and early death

Christian ethical and public responses to conversation therapies that have been inflicted on queer youth will likely be well known to people here. Probably less well known will be the fact that conversion therapies were originally developed on autistic youth and that the behaviourist techniques pioneered in the 1960s continue to be the most widely practiced form of therapeutic service provided to autistic young people in the form of “Applied Behaviour Analysis”. In 2017, a large consortium of British health, counselling and psychotherapy organisations released a memorandum of understanding on conversion therapy in the UK which described the practice as “unethical, potentially harmful and is not supported by evidence” and set out to “end the practice of conversion therapy in the UK”. There have been several significant calls for similar abolition of ABA and I’d point friends here who are interested in being a public voice of liberation to sign on to the very well organised campaign by Neurodiverse Connection (<https://ndconnection.co.uk/against-pbs-aba>), but these campaigns have been wildly different in scope and public support to the corrolary abolitionist movement for gender conversion therapy.

Framing abolitionism

We can only speculate as to the difference here, and rather than get lost in cynicism, I’d like to assess the support for abolitionism of ABA in Christian Ethics. One important and helpful clarification for those who haven’t engaged formally before with abolitionist critical theory. I’m following the work of scholars and activists like Angela Davis who suggest that abolition is a fundamentally constructive practice. When we call for the abolition of violent, cruel and oppressive practices we also make a constructive case for positive constructive change including peaceful loving alternatives.

And I’d stress at the outset that in the case of ABA there are many completely viable alternatives - if there are interested practitioners, I’d refer you to the PANDA approach (<https://www.pdasociety.org.uk/what-helps-guides/pda-approaches/panda-as-a-way-in/>), the NEST framework (<https://www.spectrumgaming.net/the-nest-approach>), and the SPACE framework (10.12968/hmed.2023.0006)

Understanding ABA

Though the title refers to analysis, ABA is only ever used for the sake of changing behaviours. [slide 1 - Examples of stimming] Pathologised and so-called antisocial behaviours have been at the core of autism diagnosis from the start. A key axis for dianosis in the most recent revision of the DSM5 refers to “persistent deficits in social communication and interaction, along with restricted and repetitive

behaviors”. I’d hasted to say that these pathologising definitions are easy to flip - neurodiversity scholars have reframed autism as involving *different* styles of social communication, along with a tendency to work through inertia and flow states and the need to self-soothe and mitigate stress through stimming. [slide 2 - account of spinning] Stimming is a wide ocean of delight, essentially various forms of sensory seeking, seeking vestibular stimulation through tapping, or proprioceptive sensory saturation through spinning in circles. Some people find it cozy to hum, and so on. Stimming is often seen as a breach of manners, and in some very limited cases stimming can be harmful, such as scratching your skin or banging body parts against hard surfaces. ABA is often very intensive, with practitioners recommending that a young person be subjected to 25 hours a week of therapy. I think we can see this intensity as an indication of the resistance of subjects to this work of behavioural deprogramming.

Stories and testimonies shared by survivors of ABA are harrowing, particularly around the use of aversive techniques which can include denying food, solitary confinement, electroshock treatment and physical abuse. Many human rights advocates have raised questions about whether practitioners using these aversive techniques and forms of exposure therapy are not in fact producing a form of torture. For the sake of my reflection here, I will bracket out these forms of treatment which are more obvious violations of the dignity and rights of vulnerable individuals. It is a common rejoinder in these conversations to point to these specific approaches as outliers, even using their extreme status to set a baseline which makes it easier to promote “mainstream” practice as ethical. This avoidance of aversive techniques is indeed what PBS practitioners sometimes point to in defense of their approaches as being less violent than ABA.

ABA consortia and practitioners emphasise that every treatment is tailored to a specific individual and generally disagree with any suggestion that there are specific default behaviours that are targetted for extinction. [slide 3 - ABA on eye-contact] Though there is an admittedly wide range within the community of ABA practitioners, there are some general trends that we can identify as being foundational to ABA. All ABA practice seeks to improve communication, develop new skills, and increase independence through techniques of behaviour modification, which are sometimes also called “positive reinforcement”. A key target for modification is non-conventional forms of communication, socialisation and RRBs (restricted and repetitive behaviours). Stimming is a major “therapeutic target”.

[slide 4 - on ABA experience] Though it is not as if we have only just discovered this fact in the last decade, there has been an increasing body of literature and emerging consensus that, as one recent study puts it, “stimming, resistance to change, and a predilection for routine” are all often “adaptive coping strategies in response to an overwhelming, novel, and ever-changing environment” [McCormackWongetal_2023, p. 2435]. ABA, even in its most benign application seeks to deprogram autistic persons from their ability to efficiently cope with stress. It is important to see this against the backdrop of research into autistic

wellbeing: the incidence of major anxiety disorders among autistic people is 2.5x (Nimmo-Smith, 2020), studies put rates of clinical depression among autistic people at 35-49%. For autistic people, suicidal ideation at 3x (Hedley et al, 2018) to 6x (Cassidy et al 2014) the general public, according to a survey by Mary Doherty with the Autscope community, (Data presented at Autscope 2020), 86% of those surveyed had experienced suicidal ideation (vs. Cassidy 2014 at and 47% had attempted suicide (35% from Cassidy 2014). Life expectancy for autistic persons is lower than average - one study (Smith, 2019) of a USA cohort has average autistic life expectancy at 39 years old, ruling out significant influence from sex / intellectual disability.

The scope of this critique extends beyond trained ABA practitioners, not least because all the different forms of ABA emphasise the training of parents, with mechanisms for monitoring of parental fidelity and retaining. So the scope of ABA practice includes parents, and the scope of ABA harms may also include children who have not undergone formal ABA therapy. Like Temple Grandin, avoiding early diagnosis likely contributed to my own avoidance of more violent treatment regimes as a child, but I can still remember the experience as a child of being constantly monitored and sanctioned by adults for fidgeting and tapping. I often wonder what pathways for self-care and stimming techniques I might have developed in another timeline. I've highlighted here the response from one respondent regarding his reasons for spinning as bringing a sense of stasis and control. This account also highlights the moral hazard that ABA, and indeed any forced behavioural intervention, will risk in intervening on the "processes and development of self-perception".

ABA is considered a growth industry, worth over \$7B in the USA alone and considered a growth industry, with high level experts exploring ways that scientific behaviour modification regimes (under different names) can be brought to prisons, care homes, schools and also established in formerly unreached nations. There is an astonishing quantity of scholarly literature on ABA and PBS, almost 400k publications on ABA - ~35k of them written since 2020. This may in part be driven by the frequent claim that ABA is an evidence-based therapy and what Alicia Broderick (2022) calls the "autism industrial complex" a massive industry devoted to training ABA therapists and deploying therapy. This research is myopic, I analysed a batch of the 783 PhD theses written on ABA since 2015 and only 11 of these engaged with the concept of trauma. Of those 11, all were devoted to caregiver fatigue, burnout and bystander trauma. This field of research is highly problematic, and meta-studies are starting to reveal how this is the case, with one relating that "Seventy percent of ABA research has been reported to involve conflicts of interest, with less than 6% of the researchers declaring the conflicts." That literature tends to foreground perspectives of practitioners, parents and carers - all potentially valid - but deeply concerning when this comes at the exclusion of lived experience by those autistic individuals experiencing the therapies.

Christian ethics:

In the limited time that I have left, I'd like to highlight some of the ways that the concerns I have analysed here might be constituted as a specifically theological ethical concern. I'd like to offer a set of affirmations as a way of capturing this:

- Let us establish as a baseline for abolition as arising when a practice or community is perpetuates violence or oppression, especially when there is a lack of freedom, e.g. this is involuntary for the person experiencing it. This is the difference between the trauma of cancer surgery and the trauma of ABA.
- It's not just that our society fails to be driven by the pull of compassion. Christians often live out moral lives which are insufficiently repulsed by violence, coercion and authoritarianism. We should be mindful that our willingness to abrogate the freedom of others in the case of so-called "antisocial" behaviours underwrites abuse of vulnerable people like children and disabled persons.
- Natural theology may have salience here: human embodied difference is not arbitrary so long as we presume that our bodies are a good gift from God carrying intention and purpose. So while I know it is contested as such, I think that the body can serve as a site for developing norms.
- However, natural law theologies are usually (with the exception of works like Vincent Lloyd's Black Natural Law) configured to neglect and even further marginalise outliers given how they are ordered around philosophical trajectories which seek to generalise, rather than being driven by a concepts of inclusivity.
- Disability, divergence and disease creates complexity for our conceptions of bodily normativity - we can see this in the context of different attitudes towards speech tics, Deafness, Blindness, and personal transformation after injury (John Swinton writes about this in the context of TBIs in *Begotten Not Made*). But complexity is not the same as incoherence and I think that a disability theology coming from lived experience can help us to navigate bodily difference.
- Any moral philosophical account that foregrounds freedom will need to be critically interrogated by autistic lived experience given the dimensions of volitional disability and cognitive difference around metacognitive function (executive function) that many autistic people experience (the philosopher John T. Maier's book on *The Disabled Will: A Theory of Addiction* is one salutary example of an attempt to reframe thinking around volition)
- Let us affirm that God's creation of bodily diversity includes differences in patterns of speech, patterns of bodily movement, modes of relating, and patterns or grammars of life which when shared can crystallise as forms of culture.
- Particularly, when those modes of expression are situated in the context of coping and emotional regulation - so long as they do not cause harm to self or others - it is an act of profound violation to forcibly extinguish the

basis for the emotional wellbeing of another person

- An autistic liberation theology presses us to grapple with queerness in behaviour as a site of God's delight and grace, and those regimes which seek to extinguish or cure autism are works of evil.